

THE KEY FEATURES AUTHENTIC MATERIALS TO DEVELOP READING SKILLS OF INTERMEDIATE LEVELS

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Annotation. The article highlights the key features of using authentic materials as an effective strategy to develop reading skills in intermediate-level learners. It emphasizes the importance of exposing students to real-life language, which enhances their comprehension abilities and cultural awareness. The article also suggests methods for selecting appropriate texts and adapting them to suit learners’ levels, encouraging engagement and motivation while building reading confidence.

Key words: reading skills, authentic materials, cultural relevance, real-life language, contextual learning, vocabulary development, skimming and scanning, critical thinking

Annotatsiya. Maqolada o'rta darajadagi o'quvchilarda o'qish ko'nikmalarini rivojlantirish uchun samarali strategiya sifatida haqiqiy materiallardan foydalanishning asosiy xususiyatlari ta'kidlangan. Bu o'quvchilarni real hayot tili bilan tanishtirish muhimligini ta'kidlaydi, bu ularning tushunish qobiliyatini va madaniy dunyo qarashini oshiradi. Maqolada, shuningdek, mos matnlarni tanlash va ularni o'quvchilar darajasiga moslashtirish, o'qishga bo'lgan ishonchni shakllantirishda faollik va motivatsiyani rag'batlantirish usullari taklif etiladi.

Kalit so'zlar: o'qish ko'nikmalari, haqiqiy materiallar, madaniy ahamiyatga ega, haqiqiy til, kontekstli o'rganish, so'z boyligini rivojlantirish, ko'rib chiqish va skanerlash, tanqidiy fikrlash

Introduction. Reading is the one of the most fundamental skills that students have to concern about how to improve it by using different methods and techniques. Developing skills can be difficult for not only elementary but also all levels can experience these challenges. Reading requires much hardworking and if the pupils fail to understand the reading over and over make them loose their interest toward these skills increasing the pupils’ level of interest and reading are on the shoulder of teachers.

Methods. There are several tips and strategies of using authentic materials for teachers to enhance the pupils reading and they might be quite useful how to develop the reading comprehension skills [1;p-463]. To develop reading in some levels such as the elementary and intermediate pupils as they vulnerable to distract easily as the result, it might be hard for them to understand the context. As a result, students have been introduced to a variety of reading materials aimed at improving their reading abilities. Singhal (2001) pointed out that certain

reading approaches rely on non-authentic or specially designed texts. These types of materials often present structured and purposeful language, which supports learners in developing grammar and vocabulary skills. Conversely, more recent reading approaches emphasize the use of texts sourced directly from the everyday communication of native speakers. [2; p.1-18]. According to Gilmore (2007), this strategy is intended to connect English language learners with authentic language as it is naturally used by native speakers. [3; p.97-118]. “It has been traditionally supposed that the language presented to learners should be simplified in some way for easy access and acquisition. Nowadays there are recommendations that the language presented should be authentic” (Widdowson 1990:67). Widdowson empathize that modification in language teaching philosophy. Traditionally, teachers thought that the best way to help pupils pick up the language keep the things simple like using slower speech, simple words and basic grammar. However, Widdowson thinks differently; using authentic materials are the kind of language people actually use in everyday life. Followers of this approach support that introduce the pupils to authentic speech, texts and media helps prepare them for real –world communication. This is not only improving their listening and reading skills, but also gives them a deeper sense of how language functions in cultural context. [4; p.3]. One of the most popular authentic materials is that NEWSPAPERS which are more powerful things for language learning [5]. They offer for pupils to boost the range of vocabulary and find easily up to date news which is relevant content for the readers. Waheeb S (2018) mentioned his article that” multiple sources of authentic materials were mentioned in the participants’ responses as these three participants indicated: *I prefer to read daily newspapers such as the Times, and our local newspaper. I like reading them in the class because they usually have interesting and enjoyable topics and themes that make us want to read more. Newspapers and magazines discuss really interesting topics. That is why we ask our teacher to read them [San]. Though reading required books, such as The Alchemist and Treasure Island, in the class benefit us, I think the class is more enjoyable when the teacher provides us with articles from different newspapers and magazines. These are current and discuss events that happened recently. The good thing is that I start to read them not only in class but also outside the class [Lin]. To me, reading the advertisement books and the restaurant menus in the class was a good and creative idea because they are really interesting and motivating. We all liked to read them, but the teacher only used them two or three times. We usually read them outside, but the idea of reading and discussing them in reading classes is great [Dani]”.*

The Waheeb S said that different type of materials is chosen not just for their content, but for what the readers immerse information which is help to them practice. Each one serves a specific linguistic teaching purpose whether it boosts their skim for main ideas, scan for details, paraphrase the message, summaries the information and organize their thoughts. In this way, authentic materials

become basic tools for building a wide range of real-world language skills. [6; p.15-34]. Many researchers have interpreted the concept of authentic materials. Marrow gave own definition to authentic materials as “stretch of real language, produced by a real speaker or writer for a real audience and designed to carry a real message of some sort” (Brown, H. D, 1991). [7; p.243]. Tomlinson says “an authentic text is one which is produced in order to communicate rather than to teach. The text does not have to be produced by a native speaker and it might be a version of an original which has been simplified to facilitate communication” (Swaffar, J. K, 1985). [8; p.15]. Zyzik and Polio determined as “those created for some real-life purpose other than language learning, and often, but not always provided by native speakers for native speakers” (Xan S, 2018). We can say that authentic materials described in different ways, but we all share a common idea: the tools like videos, podcasts, newspapers, and novels which is faced us real-life use –not just for the classroom. Nevertheless, the pupils are taught with grammar or vocabulary, they should have educated by native speaker, they show the language is used in everyday situations [8].

Results and Discussion. We assume that reading comic and manga are some of the most enjoyable ways to pick up the language. Moreover, this type of books is more interesting and can get easily attract the pupils regarding some reasons: the dialogue sounds real as acquired lots of everyday expressions, slang and even jokes .one of the most thing is artwork. The visuals help the pupils easily catch what’s going on, so even if they don’t understand every word, they can still follow the story and pick up meaning as they go. Comic and manga will not be getting bored by eager readers because the full of pictures very expressive emotions. These works will take them on their own wave. Research on using comics in foreign language classrooms often highlights their impact on improving reading skills, especially in helping students make inferences and understand meaning through context clues (Karap,2017). [8; p.11]

In conclusion, improving reading skills with an authentic material is one of the best ways to teach the pupils which are learning the language that not only enhance the pupils’ overview but also boost their all skills through the real materials. These tools help the learner interact with natural language and real contexts and also enriching their vocabulary.

References

1. Axmadaliyeva Xosiyatposhsho. PROFESSINAL TA’LIM YO’NALISHLARIDA TAHSIL OLAYOTGAN O’QUVCHILARNING INGLIZ TILIDAN KOMMUNIKATIV KOMPETENSIYASINI AUTENTIK MATERIALLAR ORQALI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH// Ижтимоий-гуманитар фанларнинг долзарб муаммолари / Актуальные проблемы социально-гуманитарных наук / Actual Problems of Humanities and Social Sciences.-2023. VL 3.-B.461-469

2. Singhal, M. (2001). Reading proficiency, reading strategies, metacognitive awareness and L2 readers. *The Reading Matrix*, 1(1), 1-8.
3. Gilmore, A. (2007). Authentic materials and authenticity in foreign language learning. *Language Teaching*, 40(02), 97-118. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0261444807004144>
4. Waheeb S. Albiladi. (2018) Exploring the Use of Written Authentic Materials in ESL Reading Classes: Benefits and Challenges. p:3.
5. Abdukhayotovna A. K. THE ROLE OF AUTHENTIC MATERIALS TO DEVELOP PUPILS' COMMUNICATIVE COMPETENCE IN ENGLISH CLASSES AT ACADEMIC LYCEUMS //Berlin Studies Transnational Journal of Science and Humanities. – 2022. – T. 2. – №. 1.5 Pedagogical sciences.
6. Widdowson, H.G. (1990) *Aspects of Language Teaching* Oxford, O.U.P.
7. Brown, H. D. (1991). *Language assessment: principles and classroom practices*. New York: Pearson Education. P:243.
8. Swaffar, J. K. (1985). Reading authentic texts in a foreign language: A cognitive model. *The Modern Language Journal* 69 (1). pp:15–34.
9. Xan, S., and others. (2018) *Kids English*. Tashkent: O'qituvchi.
10. Mona Maget Azam. Reading and Creating Comics in the Fully Online AFL Classroom: Students' Perceptions (2018). p:11